

An Autopsy based Observational Study on Pattern of Manner of death in Fall from Height at Tertiary Care Centre

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ABSTRACT

Background: Falls from height are a major cause of trauma-related mortality and present important medicolegal challenges. Accurate determination of the manner of death requires correlation of autopsy findings with circumstantial evidence. **Objectives:** This study aimed to analyze the manner of death and injury patterns in fatal fall-from-height cases subjected to medicolegal autopsy. **Materials and Methods:** the study was conducted at a tertiary care centre in Rajasthan from September 2024 to September 2025. 100 fatal fall-from-height cases were included. Data regarding demographic profile, place and height of fall, manner and mode of death, survival period, and injury patterns were studied. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and expressed as frequencies and percentages. **Results:** Males constituted 78% of cases, with the highest incidence in the 31–40 years age group (24%). Most victims belonged to rural areas (76%). Accidental falls accounted for 93% of deaths, than suicidal (5%) and homicidal (2%). Residential buildings were the most common site of occurrence (64%). Falls from heights of 10–20 feet constituted 50% of cases, while concrete surfaces were involved mostly. The head was the most frequent site of maximum impact (68%). Head injury was the leading cause of death (58%), followed by spinal cord injury (19%). Coma was the predominant mode of death (58%). **Conclusion:** Accidental falls from residential buildings onto hard surfaces were the predominant pattern of fatal falls. Severe head injuries were the principal cause of death. Enhanced fall-prevention strategies, occupational and domestic safety measures, and improved trauma care services are essential to reduce fall-related mortality. Fatal fall from height; Accidental death; Autopsy study; Head injury; Trauma mortality.

Keywords: Fall from height, Autopsy, Manner of death, Head injury, Trauma mortality

INTRODUCTION

Falls from height constitute a major public health and medicolegal problem worldwide and are among the leading causes of trauma-related morbidity and mortality. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), falls are the second leading cause of unintentional injury deaths globally, accounting for approximately 684,000 deaths annually, with a substantial burden in low- and middle-income countries.¹ The increasing pace of urbanization, construction activities, and occupational exposure to

elevated work environments has further contributed to the incidence of fall-related fatalities.

Several autopsy-based studies have demonstrated that the pattern of injuries sustained in falls from height varies according to the height of fall, body orientation at impact, and nature of the landing surface. Cranio-cerebral injuries are consistently reported as the leading cause of death, whereas spinal, thoracic, abdominal, and pelvic injuries contribute to mortality depending upon the mechanism of impact. Despite numerous international studies, regional variations continue to exist owing to differences in occupational exposure,

housing conditions, urbanization, and emergency medical services.

The pattern and severity of injuries resulting from falls depend upon several factors, including the height of the fall, surface characteristics at the point of impact, body position during landing, and individual physiological factors such as age, sex, and pre-existing medical conditions.^{2,3} High-energy impacts frequently result in multiple injuries involving the head, thorax, abdomen, pelvis, and extremities, often leading to death either instantaneously or after a variable survival period.

From a forensic perspective, fatal falls present significant challenges in determining the manner of death. Falls may occur under accidental, suicidal, homicidal, or undetermined circumstances, each having distinct medicolegal implications. Differentiation among these manners of death requires careful correlation of autopsy findings with scene investigation, police records, witness statements, and toxicological analysis.⁴ The injury pattern, distribution of external and internal injuries, and associated circumstances often provide valuable clues regarding the nature of the event. In India, rapid urban growth and increasing occupational hazards have contributed to a rising incidence of fatal falls; however, comprehensive autopsy-based studies evaluating the manner of death in such cases remain limited. Understanding the epidemiological profile and medicolegal characteristics of fall-related deaths is essential for accurate death certification, forensic reconstruction, and formulation of preventive strategies.

Rajasthan has witnessed rapid urban expansion and increasing construction activities over the past decade. However, published autopsy-based studies evaluating the medicolegal characteristics and manner of death in fatal falls from height remain scarce in this region. Such information is valuable for forensic experts, policymakers, and trauma care providers in developing preventive strategies.

The aim of this present study was to analyze the pattern of manner of death in fatal fall-from-height cases brought for medicolegal autopsy at a tertiary care centre.

Objectives

Primary Objective

To determine the pattern of manner of death among fatal fall-from-height cases subjected to medicolegal autopsy.

Secondary Objectives

- To analyze demographic characteristics.
- To study injury patterns.
- To correlate height of fall with survival period.
- To determine the cause and mode of death.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This autopsy-based descriptive prospective observational study was conducted at Tertiary care

Centre in Rajasthan, from September 2024 to September 2025. A total of 100 medico-legal autopsy cases with a history of fatal fall from height were included in the study by random sampling method.

Cases were selected by random sampling irrespective of age and sex.

Study Design

Prospective descriptive observational study.

Study Setting

Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, SMS Medical College, Jaipur.

Sample Size Calculation

As all eligible medico-legal autopsy cases during the study period were included, no formal sample size calculation was performed.

Sampling technique

Consecutive sampling was adopted.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 24.0. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included all cases with a documented history of fall from height that were brought for medicolegal autopsy, provided that written informed consent for participation in the study had been obtained from the attendants or legally authorized representatives of the deceased. Cases involving putrefied bodies and those in which death was attributed to an associated medical cause, such as myocardial infarction, cerebral stroke, or other significant natural diseases, rather than the fall itself, were excluded from the study. Written informed consent was obtained from the legal representatives (next of kin) of the deceased before data collection, as the study involved collecting demographic information and incidence history. Consent was obtained to ensure ethical compliance and protect participants' privacy and confidentiality.

Data regarding socio-demographic characteristics, circumstances of the incident, manner and mode of death, and injury patterns were collected from police records, hospital documents, relatives, and autopsy findings using a pre-designed proforma. Detailed external and internal examinations were performed in all cases, and the cause of death was determined based on autopsy findings and relevant investigation reports. The collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistical methods (SPSS 24). Results were expressed as frequencies & percentages wherever applicable.

The study was conducted after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee.

RESULTS

During the study period, approximately 4500–5000 medico-legal autopsies were performed in study center Medical College, out of which 100 fatal cases of fall from height fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included.

The study demonstrated a clear male predominance, with males constituting 78% of cases. The most commonly affected age group was 31–40 years, followed by individuals above 60 years of age, indicating involvement of both economically productive and elderly populations.

Table 1: Age and Sex wise distribution of autopsy cases of fall from height

Age (yrs)	Sex				Total (%)
	Male		Female		
	No.	%	No.	%	
0-10	3	3%	7	7%	10%
11-20	2	2%	1	1%	3%
21-30	10	10%	3	3%	13%
31-40	24	24%	0	0%	24%
41-50	11	11%	5	5%	16%
51-60	9	9%	2	2%	11%
>60	19	19%	4	4%	23%
Total	78	78%	22	22%	100(100%)

Most victims belonged to rural areas (76%) compare with urban areas (24%), Hindu population (84%) compare to Muslim (16%) and Half of the cases were educated up to the **primary level (50%)**, followed by **illiterates (22%)**. Secondary and graduate-level education accounted for **16%** and **12%** of cases, respectively. Males predominated at all educational levels, indicating that **lower educational status was more common among the study subjects**, highlighting the role of socio-economic and environmental factors.

The majority of falls occurred in **residential buildings (64 cases, 64%)**, comprising **60 accidental, 3 suicidal, and 1 homicidal case**. This was followed by **workplaces (17 cases, 17%)**, **construction sites (9 cases, 9%)**, and **farms/jungles (6 cases, 6%)**, where most cases were accidental. **Public places accounted for 4 cases (4%)**, including **2 accidental, 1 suicidal, and 1 homicidal case**. Overall, accidental falls predominated at all places of incidence.

Figure 1: Distribution of autopsy cases of fall from height according to manner of death and Incidence place

The majority of incidents occurred during daytime hours, particularly between 12:00 and 18:00 hours (40%).

Table 2: Distribution of autopsy cases of fall from height according to manner of death and height of fall

Height of fall	Accidental	Suicidal	Homicidal	No. of cases
Less than 5 feet	11	00	00	11
5-10 Feet	26	00	00	26
10- 20 feet	47	02	01	50
>20 feet	09	03	01	13
Total	93	05	02	100

The most common height of fall was **10–20 feet (50 cases, 50%)**, including **47 accidental, 2 suicidal, and 1 homicidal case**. This was followed by **5–10 feet (26 cases, 26%)**, **more than 20 feet (13 cases, 13%)**, and **less than 5 feet (11 cases, 11%)**. Suicidal falls were more frequent from **heights greater than 20 feet (3 cases)**,

Concrete (hard) surface was the most common surface of fall, accounting for **82 cases (82%)**, including **75 accidental, 5 suicidal, and 2 homicidal cases**. Grass (soft) surface was involved in **17 cases (17%)**, while sand (soft) surface accounted for **1 case (1%)**. Accidental falls constituted the majority of cases across all types of surfaces.

The **head** was the most common site of maximum impact, accounting for **68%** of cases, followed by the **back (16%)** and **chest (7%)**. Other regions such as the abdomen (5%) and neck, gluteal region, pelvic region, and lower limbs (1% each) were infrequently involved. Overall, **head impact predominated as the maximum impact site in the majority of cases**.

Table 3: Distribution of autopsy cases of fall from height according to mode of death and Site of maximum impact

Major cause leading to fatality	Coma	Shock			Total Cases
		Spinal	Hemorrhagic	Septicaemic	
Head injury	58	00	00	00	58
Spinal Cord Injuries	00	17	00	02	19
Multiple Bodily Injuries	00	02	07	01	10
Abdominal Injuries	00	00	02	03	05
Thoracic Injuries	00	00	05	00	05
Pelvic Injuries	00	00	03	00	03
Total	58	19	17	06	100

Head injury was the leading cause of death, followed by spinal cord injury and multiple bodily injuries. Coma was the most common mode of death, followed by shock, predominantly spinal and hemorrhagic shock.

Table 4: Distribution of autopsy cases of fall from height according Height of fall and Survival Period

Survival Period	Height of fall				Total (%)
	Less than 5 feet	5-10 Feet	10- 20 feet	More than 20 feet	
Brought death	00	00	06	04	10 (10%)
0-6 hours	01	02	06	03	12 (12%)
7-12 hours	00	01	05	02	08 (08%)
13- 24 hours	02	03	02	02	09 (09%)
25-48 hours	00	05	07	01	13 (13%)
49-72 hours	02	06	04	00	12 (12%)
4 to 7 days	03	04	08	01	16 (16%)
8 to 15 days	03	05	10	00	18 (18%)
16 to 30 days	00	00	02	00	02 (02%)
Total	11	26	50	13	100 (100%)

A substantial proportion of victims survived beyond the immediate post-injury period, indicating a potential window for medical intervention.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, fatal falls from height accounted for approximately 2–2.2% of all medico-legal autopsies conducted during the study period. A clear male predominance (78%) was observed, with the highest incidence in the 31–40 years age group, followed by

individuals above 60 years. Similar findings have been reported by Murthy et al., Ahmed et al., Sharma et al., and Ramachandran et al., who attributed the increased incidence among males to **greater occupational exposure (construction, industrial and agricultural work), higher outdoor activity, increased risk-taking**

behaviour, greater involvement in physically demanding occupations, and more frequent alcohol or substance use during work or leisure activities.

Elderly individuals are more vulnerable because of age-related decline in balance, muscle strength, vision, and mobility, which increases the risk of falls.⁶⁻⁹

Most victims belonged to rural areas (76%) and had low educational status, suggesting the influence of socio-economic and environmental factors. **The higher incidence in rural areas may be due to unsafe housing, agricultural occupations, and limited access to emergency care, while low educational status may reflect poor awareness of safety measures and greater employment in high-risk occupations.** Residential buildings were the most common place of incidence (64%), **likely because of unprotected rooftops, inadequate safety barriers, and household activities at height.** Workplaces and construction sites were also common, **owing to work at heights and inadequate use of safety equipment.** Similar observations have been reported by Saritha and Sasikala, Sagina et al., and Lakshmy et al., emphasizing the importance of domestic and occupational safety measures.¹⁰⁻¹²

Most incidents occurred during daytime (12:00–18:00 hours), likely because this period coincides with peak occupational, agricultural, construction, and household activities, resulting in greater exposure to fall hazards. Falls from heights of 10–20 feet constituted half of all cases, followed by falls from 5–10 feet. Comparable findings have been reported by Arbes and Berzlanovich, Ramadan et al., and Lohanathan et al., indicating that fatal injuries may occur even from moderate heights.¹³⁻¹⁵ Concrete was the most common impact surface (82%), which is associated with greater injury severity because of minimal energy absorption at impact.^{2,3} This suggests that the severity of injury depends not only on the height of the fall but also on factors such as the impact surface, body position at impact, and the body region sustaining the primary impact.

Accidental falls accounted for the vast majority of cases (93%), whereas suicidal (5%) and homicidal (2%) falls were relatively uncommon. This pattern is consistent with previous studies and highlights accidental falls as the principal public health concern. From a forensic perspective, differentiation between accidental, suicidal, and homicidal falls is essential because each has distinct medicolegal implications. Accidental falls commonly occur during routine household activities, construction work, or agricultural work. Suicidal falls typically involve intentional jumping from rooftops, terraces, bridges, or high-rise buildings. Homicidal falls are uncommon and may result from pushing the victim from a height or throwing an unconscious or incapacitated person over an edge. Accurate determination of the manner of death requires careful correlation of scene findings, autopsy injuries, witness

statements, and circumstantial evidence to ensure proper administration of justice.

The head was the most common site of maximum impact (68%), and head injury was the leading cause of death (58%), with coma being the predominant mode of death. Similar findings have been documented by Lau, Ahmed et al., Vadysinghe et al., and Kumar et al., highlighting the critical role of cranio-cerebral trauma in fatal falls.^{5,7,16,17} The predominance of head injuries is attributable to the head frequently striking the ground first and the limited capacity of the skull and brain to withstand high-impact forces. Spinal cord injuries were the second most common cause of death, consistent with observations by Turgut et al. and Shkrum and Ramsay.^{18,19}

A substantial proportion of victims survived for several hours to days after injury, with the largest group surviving between 8 and 15 days. This finding suggests that timely trauma care and advanced critical care management may improve survival outcomes. Overall, accidental falls from residential buildings onto hard surfaces resulting in severe head injuries constituted the predominant pattern observed in the present study.

The accidental falls were 93%, suicidal were 5% and homicidal were 2% cases.

The findings of the present study reinforce the importance of meticulous medico-legal investigation in all fatal falls from height. Correlation of autopsy findings with scene investigation and circumstantial evidence significantly improves the accuracy of determining the manner of death and contributes to the administration of justice.

CONCLUSION

Fatal falls from height constituted an important cause of medico-legal mortality, predominantly affecting males and individuals in the economically productive age group. Most victims belonged to rural areas and had lower educational status, indicating the influence of socio-economic and environmental factors. Accidental falls were the most common manner of death, with residential buildings being the principal site of occurrence.

Falls from moderate heights (10–20 feet) onto hard concrete surfaces accounted for the majority of fatalities. Head impact was the most frequent site of maximum impact, and head injury was the leading cause of death, with coma being the predominant mode of death. Spinal cord injuries represented the second most common fatal injury.

A considerable proportion of victims survived for several hours to days following the incident, highlighting a potential window for effective medical intervention. The findings emphasize the need for improved domestic and occupational safety measures, public awareness regarding fall prevention, and strengthening of trauma care services to reduce mortality associated with falls from height. Furthermore, careful correlation of scene findings with

autopsy observations remains essential for accurate determination of the manner and cause of death in medico-legal investigations.

Future multicentric studies with larger sample sizes and incorporation of toxicological, radiological, and biomechanical analyses are recommended to improve understanding of fatal fall mechanisms.

Strength of the Study

- Prospective autopsy-based design.
- Comprehensive evaluation of demographic, injury, and medico-legal variables.
- Inclusion of manner, cause, mode, survival period, and impact site.
- Provides regional data from Rajasthan where similar studies are limited.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

- The study was conducted at a **single tertiary care center** with a **limited sample size (100 cases)**, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.
- Only **fatal autopsy cases** were included; non-fatal falls were not studied.
- Some **circumstantial information** (e.g., alcohol use, psychiatric history, and exact mechanism of fall) was incomplete or unavailable.
- Being an **observational study**, causal relationships could not be established.
- Toxicological findings and psychiatric history were not available for all cases, limiting complete assessment of suicidal falls.

Future Recommendations

- Improve rooftop safety.
- Mandatory safety harnesses.
- Occupational awareness programmes.
- Early trauma referral.
- Multicentric research.

ETHICAL COMMITTEE APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee and Institutional Research Review Board of SMS Medical College, Jaipur (Ref. No. 1088/MC/EC/2024 dated 23-10-2024).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None to declare

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Falls. Geneva: WHO; 2021.
2. Huelke DF, Compton CP. Injury mechanisms in falls from heights. *J Trauma*. 1983;23(10):876-80.
3. Chadwick EK, Nicol AC, Lane JV, Gray TG. Biomechanics of falls. *Injury*. 1991;22(6):487-91.
4. Saukko P, Knight B. *Knight's Forensic Pathology*. 4th ed. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2016. p. 188-201.
5. DiMaio VJ, DiMaio D. *Forensic Pathology*. 2nd ed. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2001. p. 285-94.
6. Vasudeva Murthy CR, Prasad BK, Kumar GP. Study of pattern of injuries in fatal cases of fall from height. *J Indian Acad Forensic Med*. 2012;34(1):45-49.
7. Ahmed M, Rahman MZ, Hossain MA, Akhter S. Pattern of fatal injury in fall from height cases: A medicolegal study. *J Dhaka Med Coll*. 2013;22(1):26-32.
8. Sharma B, Yadav A, Meena GS. Epidemiological and pattern of injuries due to fall from height: A retrospective study. *J Indian Acad Forensic Med*. 2022;44(3):245-250.
9. Ramachandran S, Kumaravel P, Subramanian K. Pattern of deaths due to fall from height: A prospective study. *Indian J Forensic Med Toxicol*. 2023;17(2):112-118.
10. Saritha SR, Sasikala K. Pattern and socio-demographic profile of victims of fall from height into water: An autopsy study. *J Indian Acad Forensic Med*. 2015;37(2):132-136.
11. Sagina KR, Rao V, Prasad M. Correlation between crime scene and pattern of injuries in deaths due to fall from height. *J Forensic Med Sci Law*. 2023;32(1):45-50.
12. Lakshmy S, Pranap Kumar P, Kachare RV, Charuletha D. An autopsy-based study on pattern of fatal injuries in fall from height. *J Indian Acad Forensic Med*. 2024;46(3):325-329.
13. Arbes S, Berzlanovich A. Injury pattern in correlation with the height of fatal falls. *Forensic Sci Int*. 2015;257:257-261.
14. Ramadan AF, Soliman EM, Abo El-Noor MM, Shahin MM. Patterns of injuries in fatal fall from height cases: Autopsy study.

- Egypt J Forensic Sci Appl Toxicol. 2020;20(4):1-15.
15. Lohanathan A, Soundappan S, Prabhakaran A. An elucidation of pattern of injuries in patients with fall from height. Int J Emerg Med. 2020;13(1):48.
 16. Vadysinghe AN, Senanayake S, Edirisinghe PA. Fatalities following fall from heights presented to medico-legal units in Sri Lanka. Forensic Sci Int. 2023;344:111553.
 17. Kumar R, et al. Patterns of head injuries in fatal fall from heights. Indian J Forensic Med Toxicol. 2024.
 18. Turgut K, Sarihan ME, Colak C, et al. Demographic characteristics of falls from height and their impact on mortality. Ulus Travma Acil Cerrahi Derg. 2018;24(2):136-143.
 19. Shkrum MJ, Ramsay DA. Forensic Pathology of Trauma. 1st ed. Totowa: Humana Press; 2007. p.425.